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Rec8 induction resulting from expression of the ATG16L1 variant that confers risk for IBD.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

The findings point to a genomic instability event that occurs following loss of homeostasis induced by endogenous expression of a disease associated variant leading to disease onset.

Citations

1. Watanabe, Y. and Nurse, P., 1999. Cohesin Rec8 is required for reductional chromosome segregation at meiosis. Nature, 400(6743), pp.461-464.